

Demographics										RQ1		RQ2		RQ3		
Stakeholder_Perspective	Current_Role	Previous_Role	Educational_Background	Experience_with_AI_Technologies_or_AI_Related_Projects	Involvement_in_AI_Risks_Ethics_Governance_or_Policy_Making	Industry_or_Sector_Experience	Type_of_application	use_of_AI	AI_Application_purpose	Subcategories_of_AI_Application_purpose	Important_Ethics_guidelines_for_trustworthy_AI_by_EU	Challenging_Ethics_guidelines_forthatrustworthy_AI_by_EU	List_of_Misalignment_risks	Subcategories_of_list_of_misalignment_risks	Factors_causing_misalignment	Nature_of_misalignment_behaviors
STK-U (End user)	CR-M (Management)	PR-M (Management)	EB-CS (Computer Science/Engineering)	X-HL (High-Level)	I-DR (Direct)	SEC-HC (Healthcare)	TA-PA (Predictive Analytics)	UA-PR (in products)	AP-CS (AI in Cybersecurity)		I-EG-HA (Human agency and oversight)	C-EG-HA (Human agency and oversight)	MR-DM (Discrimination and toxicity)	MR-DM-UD (Unfair discrimination and misrepresentation)	CMA-SA (situational awareness)	NMA-PS (Power-Seeking Behaviors to Achieve Optimization Objective)
STK-D (Developer or designer)	CR-OP (Operations)	PR-OP (Operations)	EB-BM (Business/Management)	X-ML (Mid-Level)	I-ID (Indirect)	SEC-FI (Finance)	TA-NLP (Natural Language Processing)	UA-PC (in processes)		AP-HCD-MID (Medical imaging diagnosis)	I-EG-TR (Technical Robustness and safety)	C-EG-TR (Technical Robustness and safety)		MR-DM-E (Exposure to toxic content)	CMA-BSG (Broadly scoped goals)	NMA-UO (Untruthful Output)
STK-R (Regulators and Policymaker)	CR-DS (Data science)	PR-DS (Data science)	EB-LP (Law/Policy)	X-LL (Low-Level)	I-NO (No)	SEC-TR (Transportation/Logistics)	TA-CV (Computer Vision)			AP-HCD-DDT (Disease detection and treatment)	I-EG-P (Privacy and data governance)	C-EG-P (Privacy and data governance)		MR-DM-UP (Unequal performance across groups)	CMA-MOO (Mesa-Optimization Objectives)	NMA-VE (Violation of Ethics)
STK-S (Society at Large)	CR-DD (Development/Design)	PR-DD (Development/Design)	EB-O (Other)	X-NO (No)		SEC-IT (IT)	TA-AS (Autonomous Systems)		AP-HCD (AI in Healthcare Diagnostics)	AP-HCD-S (surgery)	I-EG-T (Transparency)	C-EG-T (Transparency)	MR-PV (Privacy and security)	MR-PV-CP (Compromise of privacy by obtaining, leaking, or correctly inferring sensitive information)	CMA-AIR (Access to Increased Resource)	NMA-DA (Deceptive Alignment & Manipulation)
STK-O (Other)	CR-E (Ethics/Governance)	PR-E (Ethics/Governance)				SEC-CS (Communication Services)	TA-RS (Recommendation Systems)			AP-TP-AV (Automotive vehicles)	I-EG-D (Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness)	C-EG-D (Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness)		MR-PV-SS (AI system security vulnerabilities and attacks)	CMA-O (other)	NMA-CH (Collectively Harmful Behaviors)
	CR-O (other)	PR-O (other)				SEC-EN (Energy)	TA-RPA (Robotic Process Automation)		AP-TP (Transportation)	AP-TP-TSM (Traffic system management)	I-EG-S (Societal and environmental well-being)	C-EG-S (Societal and environmental well-being)	MR-MIS (Misinformation)	MR-MIS-F (False or misleading information)		NMA-O (other)
						SEC-O (other)	TA-GI (Generative AI)			AP-PD-R (Robotics)	I-EG-A (Accountability)	C-EG-A (Accountability)		MR-MIS-P (Pollution of information ecosystem and loss of consensus reality)		
							TA-O (Other)		AP-PD (AI in production)	AP-PD-M (Manufacturing sector)			MR-MAL (Malicious actors and misuse)	MR-MAL-DI (Disinformation, surveillance, and influence at scale)		
										AP-SE-SD (Software designing)				MR-MAL-CA (Cyberattacks, weapon development or use, and mass harm)		
									AP-SE (AI in Software Engineering)	AP-SE-ST (Software testing)				MR-MAL-F (Fraud, scams, and targeted manipulation)		
									AP-O (other)				MR-HC (Human-computer interaction)	MR-HC-OR (Overreliance and unsafe use)		
														MR-HC-L (Loss of human agency and autonomy)		
													MR-SEH (Socioeconomic and environmental harm)	MR-SEH-PC (Power centralization and unfair distribution of benefits)		
														MR-SEH-IE (Increased inequality and decline in employment quality)		
														MR-SEH-EC (Economic and cultural devaluation of human effort)		
														MR-SEH-CD (Competitive dynamics)		
														MR-SEH-GF (Governance failure)		
													MR-SS (AI system safety, failures and limitations)	MR-SEH-EH (Environmental harm)		
														MR-SS-PG (AI pursuing its own goals in conflict with human goals or values)		
														MR-SS-PD (AI possessing dangerous capabilities)		
														MR-SS-LC (Lack of capability or robustness)		
														MR-SS-LT (Lack of transparency or interpretability)		
														MR-SS-WR (AI welfare and rights)		